

HISTORY OF THE "ESKI ANHOR" CANAL

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ABSTRACT

One of the irrigation facilities built by the Soviet government in the 50s and 70s of the 20th century in the Kashkadarya region is the history of the construction of the "Eski Anhor" canal.

Even at the beginning of the new third millennium, agriculture remains one of the main sectors of the Central Asian economy. Historically, irrigated agriculture has played an important role in the life of the peoples of this region. Reservoirs and irrigation canals, which are the largest waterworks in the Kashkadarya oasis, were built between 1950 and 1980, and today they are still the main irrigation facilities in the region.

The problem of water supply and its quality in industry and agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the fate of the population living in the lands developed during the Soviet era, is related to water, is even more

important in the process of global climate change.

Today, it is known that "the existing irrigation infrastructure, most of the pumping stations in the country have been in use for more than thirty to forty years and are in need of reconstruction or overhaul" [1].

Although there are 55 reservoirs with a total volume of 19.2 billion m³ in the country [2], the Kashkadarya oasis is characterized by the specificity and complexity of the water problem.

In the Kashkadarya region in one hydrological year 4.5-5.0 billion. m³ water is consumed. 75% of the required water resources are formed from the territory of neighboring Turkmenistan, ie from the Amudarya in

the Karshi main canal, the remaining 5% from the Zarafshan river, 20% through the Kashkadarya and its tributaries [3]. Demographic growth in the region, the process of industrialization and the great need for water in agriculture require modern approaches to the use of water and water facilities.

The issue of scientific study and development of the history of irrigation of the Kashkadarya oasis dates back to the colonial policy of the Russian Empire. For example, in 1880, an engineer prepared a project to irrigate the Karshi desert with water from the Amudarya through the Lessar canal. However, the study of water resources and land resources in the oasis began in full after 1925, after the establishment of Soviet power.

LV Dunin-Barkovsky, one of the leading researchers in the field of irrigation, notes in [6] that the water of the Amudarya and Zarafshan rivers can develop irrigation in Uzbekistan. The government's goal in developing the Karshi desert was to extract hundreds of thousands of tons of quality white gold. To this end, the Soviet state had to look for additional water sources to develop cotton growing in the oasis.

The Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic has been focusing on the reconstruction of the Old Anhar Canal since 1948 [7] as a solution to the problem.

One of the experts in the field of water management in Uzbekistan, Salijon Mamarasulov, in his work [8] notes that the Old Anhar Canal was excavated in the first century BC.

In a 1946 study of the history of the Old Anhar Canal, formerly known as Manas [9], archaeologists identified A. I. Terenojkin and L. I. Albaumlar, S. in 1954. K. Kabanov [10] conducted effective scientific research.

In 1952, the Sredazgiprovodkhlopok Design Institute developed the Land and Water Use Scheme of the Kashkadarya Irrigation Region. The construction project of the old Anhar canal was a prelude to the development of the Karshi desert.

Since the 1950s, the government has made decisions and allocated funds for the construction of various facilities on new irrigation networks in the oasis.

In 1953, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Republic decided to reconstruct the Old Anhar Canal.

The old Anhar Canal was reconstructed in 1954 and commissioned in 1955. [13] Through this canal, the possibility of irrigating the lands of today's Karshi and Kasan districts, mainly in Chirakchi district, has increased.

The route of the Old Anhar Canal runs through the desert in the south-western direction, with a height difference of 300 meters at the beginning and end of the canal.

The builders removed a 17-meter-high, 83-meter-long dam from the Dargam canal, which draws water from the Zarafshan River, and removed the head of the 184-kilometer-long Old Anhar canal. Thousands of hard-working hashers from Kashkadarya, Samarkand and Bukhara dug canals.

In 1956, more than 10,000 hectares of land were developed through the Old Anhar Canal to the Pistali massif of the Karshi desert, the Kokdala and Akhunboboev state farms in the Chirakchi district, and the collective farms and state farms in the Beshkent zone of the Karshi district. However, the water of this canal alone was not enough to develop the Karshi desert, which is drying up hundreds of thousands of hectares, and to get a lot of cotton.

The government began construction of the Chimkurgan Reservoir in the middle reaches of the Kashkadarya River in 1957 in the Kamashi district, which was first developed by the Sredazgiprovdkhlopok design institute in 1954 to store 500 million cubic meters of water. After the commissioning of the reservoir, cotton production increased in the middle and lower reaches of the Kashkadarya oasis.

With the launch of the Chimkurgan Reservoir, it was possible to irrigate 70,000 hectares of crops in the lower Kashkadarya region. The Chimkurgan Reservoir and the Old Anhar Canal have become large structures that will greatly benefit the oasis economy.

Experts have also found that an average of 500-550 million cubic meters of water discharged from the Old Anhar Canal each year is wasted by evaporating or evaporating 165-180 million cubic meters [20]. In fact, experts knew how much a drop of water in the oasis was worth in cotton growing, and that the judicious use of

water yielded thousands of tons of cotton.

On November 6, 1970, the Ministry of Land Reclamation and Water Resources of the Uzbek SSR approved the "Re-excavation project of the Old Anhar Canal" prepared under the leadership of engineer N. Balunov [21]. In September 1971, construction began on a new canal in the Old Anhar Canal. The construction of a new canal has played a significant role in partially eliminating water shortages in Kashkadarya region.

"Eskiangarkanalroy" established by the order of the Ministry of Agriculture of the USSR No. 229 of 22 / X-1971 dated 1921 [24] was the head.

The construction of the new channel of the old Anhar canal was attended by the regional department of water resources, the regional association "Uzselkhoztekhnika", the regional automobile trust, the regional state farm trust [25] and many construction organizations of the region.

The new channel of the old Anhar canal is 43.5 km long, starting from the village of Ulus in the Samarkand region and extending to the Kumdarya canal [26]. The 12-kilometer section of the old Anhar canal, a 600-meter-long culvert, the main hydroelectric station and the Karshi-Samarkand railway bridge were built by the builders of the Samarkandvodstroy trust [27]. Along with the new channel of the old Anhar canal, large-scale construction works have been carried out in Kumdarya, a small river in Chirakchi district.

In the autumn of 1970, 20 excavators, 15 bulldozers and many other equipment were used to excavate 15 km of

sandstone in Kumdarya[28]. In October 1971, more than 1 million cubic meters of earthworks were carried out in the village of Uyshin, Chirakchi district, from the beginning of the Old Anhar Canal.

In December 1971, under the leadership of the Department of Irrigation Networks of Chirakchi district alone, workers from the district were allocated 4.1 km of the new riverbed of the Old Anhar Canal. It is planned to lay 1,050 cubic meters of concrete, which will involve 1,300 workers, 11 water trucks, 220 DN equipment and other equipment[30].

Beginning in December 1971, the concreting of the canal began on a large scale, with three concrete plants in operation[31]. The bottom of the canal is 2.6 meters long, 7.1 meters high and 15 meters wide, with 2.5 cubic meters of concrete per pogrameter[32].

Excavation of the 31.5-kilometer section of the canal was carried out by the people of Kashkadarya. From autumn 1971 to December 1972, 20 million cubic meters of earthworks were carried out and more than fifteen hydraulic structures were built[33]. Aid forces from other regions of the country also came to Kashkadarya for the construction of the old Anhar canal.

In the early winter of 1972, more than 700 vehicles were involved in canal construction. 100 of them came from Namangan, Andijan, Tashkent and Bukhara regions[34].

In August 1972, water from the Zarafshan River flowed through the new channel of the Old Anhar Canal[35] and 50 million cubic meters of water from the canal flowed into the Chimkurgan Reservoir[36]. In 1971, Kashkadarya region harvested 253

thousand tons of cotton [37], and in 1972 the region gave 343 thousand tons of cotton[38]. As a result, the cotton harvest in the oasis increased significantly in one year.

The old Anhar canal was commissioned in May 1974 and the government renamed it the Moscow Canal. Since this year, the canal has received 263 million cubic meters of water annually. Ninety percent of the water flowing from the canal will be fully utilized. The canal will supply water to 65,000 hectares of land. A total of 30.2 million cubic meters of soil, 256,000 cubic meters of concrete and reinforced concrete works were carried out in the new channel of the canal[39].

The new channel of the canal joins Kashkadarya from the border of Pakhtakor collective farm of Shahrisabz district. More than 10,000 people and 2,000 mechanics from our region took part in the construction of the canal[40].

In 1974, the republic produced 5.3 million tons of cotton[41]. In 1974, 371,000 tons [42] of cotton were harvested in Kashkadarya region. In 1974, the cotton yield in the region increased from 26.5 quintals in 1970 to 29.5 quintals [43]. The Ulyanov collective farm in Kasan district, which specializes in the production of fine-fiber cotton, delivered 13,000 tons of cotton to the state in four years (1970-1974)[44].

Irrigation and water means the acquisition of many new lands, as well as an abundant harvest of cotton in a climate-friendly area. Scientific

research shows that the main goal of the Soviet government's irrigation construction in Uzbekistan in the 1950s

and 1980s, particularly in the Kashkadarya oasis, was to grow cotton.

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